

SOCIO-ECONOMIC BACKGROUND AND PRE-ENROLMENT PREPARATION OF ENGINEERING STUDENTS: AN EMPIRICAL INVESTIGATION

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to investigate the socio-economic background and pre-enrolment preparation of the Bachelor of Technology students of Dibrugarh University Institute of Engineering and Technology (DUIET). The regulations concerning the student's admission into technical colleges in Assam were also analysed. In this study, data was collected from a sample of 100 B. Tech students from the four branches of engineering offered by the institute. A descriptive survey method of research was used, and a closed-ended questionnaire was utilised to gather primary data, while the document review method was used to gather secondary data. The findings of this research revealed that a majority of B. Tech students of DUIET come from well-to-do socio-economic backgrounds, with 77% having parents with assets and nearly 70% of them having parents making an annual income of over 3 lakhs. The study also discovered that 52% of students had both parents working. The research, however, discovered that the students from the Scheduled Caste and Scheduled Tribe communities were still underrepresented in the Institute, especially the female students. It was also discovered that the admission rules and regulations are the same for public or government technical institutions, but private technical institutions conduct the admission process under their own set of rules. Nonetheless, the study found that the Assam government reservation policy for seats in technical education applied to both public and private technical institutes. Future studies should build on this by extending to other technical institutions to see if the socio-economic patterns are similar.

Keywords: Socio-Economic Background, B. Tech Students, B. Tech Programs, Pre-Enrolment Preparation

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1. INTRODUCTION

In today's world, the socio-economic background of individuals is a crucial tool that is being used to gauge the social development of any sort within societies. According to Thomson (2018), socio-economic background is represented by the index of economic, social and cultural status of people. He further argues that socioeconomic background can comprise of parental occupation, parental level of education and income of the parents. In other words, a combination of factors such as the economy, occupation, income, wealth, neighbourhood etc. are the components that form the socio-economic status of individuals. In recent years, the socioeconomic conditions of people have been improving in many developing countries.

Access to education in developing countries has improved the social and economic conditions of people in the last few years. Burchi (2006) says that education has resulted in improved methods of farming, and this ultimately increases agricultural productivity. This allows people to have proper diets that improve their health, and they sell surplus produce for profits, thereby improving their financial and economic conditions. Saikia, Khanikor, and Dutta (2022) argue that people's lifestyles depend on their economic conditions and their positions in society are influenced by the income they generate. Research indicates that people's lifestyles, choices of careers, schools to enrol into, and whether or not they should move to rural or urban areas are all influenced by their socioeconomic status. High socio-economic status is influenced by factors such as access to education. Mukudi (2003) cited in Burchi (2006), contends that 'education has a key role in accessing public information, especially information concerning health, nutrition and hygiene.' He further stresses that educated and informed people have more probability to select valuable objectives in life, such as having stable access to food for their households.' This solidifies the notion that, indeed, education can be of great significance in improving people's social and economic conditions. These socio-economic factors or conditions help in the categorisation of people into different sections within societies in an effort to identify socioeconomic inequalities and uneven power distribution. They help government authorities identify groups of people who may need the most social and economic help. Over the past few years, researchers have conducted a handful of studies in the area of people's socio-economic status for many different purposes in Assam and other areas of the country. However, it was discovered from those previous studies that little to no research has been done on the B. Tech Students of Dibrugarh University Institute of Engineering & Technology (DUIET) located in Dibrugarh University campus, Dibrugarh, Assam. Therefore, this study's focus is narrowed to that particular group of people. The present study aims to study the socio-economic background of this particular group of students and their pre-enrolment preparation for the engineering programmes. The study will also analyse the government of Assam regulations for selecting and admitting students into technical colleges and institutes across the state.

1.1. History of engineering education in India: Chinn et al. (2019) says that engineering is the practical application of science accomplished through knowledge, mathematics, and practical experience applied to the design of useful objects or processes. He further states that engineering is the discipline of acquiring and applying scientific and technical knowledge to design, analyse, and/or construct works for practical purposes. It is a profession in which a knowledge of mathematical and natural sciences gained by study, experience, and practice is applied with judgement to develop ways to utilise the materials and forces of nature

economically for the benefit of humankind. Professional practitioners of engineering are called Engineers (Chinn et al, 2019). Engineering education in India began as early as the time of British rule in the country, and it focused on civil engineering. During this time, Chinn et al. (2019) stressed that engineering education in the country was based on the British model, which laid emphasis on professional practice. In 1847, the engineering college at Roorkee was established, and Poona Civil Engineering College was established in 1854 in Pune (Chinn et al., 2019). Bengal Engineering College in Shibpur (1856), Banaras Hindu University (1916), Harcourt Butler Technological Institute, Kanpur (1920) was one of the earliest engineering colleges established and continues to this day. In 1945, the Sarkar Committee was appointed to suggest options for advanced technological education in India (Chinn et al, 2019). Chinn et al (2019) further state that The Sarkar Committee recommended the establishment of higher technological institutes based on the Massachusetts Institute of Technology in the four regions of India. This resulted in the setting up of the five Indian Institutes of Technology at Kharagpur (1959), Bombay (1958), Kanpur (1959), Madras (1960) and Delhi (1961) (Delhi was added to the original four). The All India Council for Technical Education was set up in 1945 to oversee all technological education (diploma, degree and postgraduate) in the country.

According to Jha et al (2010), the British Indian government established the first survey school in 1794 in Madras with only eight boys' students from English schools. The British policy during this time was against teaching surveying to native Indians because of the military and political implications of survey work, as a precaution against reliable maps falling into the hands of the French, the Dutch and the Portuguese. The Madras Survey School went through several ups to the point where it almost shut down, but it was revived in 1819. The survey school was later expanded in 1857 and renamed the civil engineering school (Jha et al., 2010). Saha & Ghosh (2011) add to Chin's contribution by detailing that technical education in India began in three models: the colonial model, the nationalistic model and the research model. He adds that in the early stages of technical education, in the colonial model, colonialists wanted to train countrymen as subservient workers only. He adds that five engineering colleges were established to produce 'Technical hands' for the empire. The curriculum and the training in these colleges were geared mostly to meet the requirements of only subordinate grades of engineering services of then colonial India (Saha & Ghosh, 2011).

1.2. The present status of engineering education in India: One of the various ways that could help describe the current status of engineering education in India is the growth of the institutions. The establishment of the university system for engineering education began in 1957, and it has seen tremendous growth since then (Saha & Ghosh, 2011). Following independence, the country saw a growth in the number of technical institutions. The number of universities has increased from 25 in 1950 to 346 in 2008, the number of engineering degree level institutions has increased from 44 to 1668, and the number of colleges has increased from 700 to 18064, with the enrolment from 0.1 million to 11.2 million (Saha & Ghosh, 2011). According to Mohan, the current state of engineering education owes its success to the work done by the All India Council for Technical Education (AICTE). AICTE has overseen the coordinated development of engineering education in India. AICTE expanded engineering education in India over the decades by adding capacity and creating an academic ambience for nurturing and supporting quality education across the country. Today, about 3,500 institutions are disseminating engineering education in India. However, it is observed that enrolment in various engineering courses has been on the decline in the country since 2012-13 (Mohan). It is also observed that about 50.2% of all engineering seats are located in the five Southern states of India – Andhra Pradesh, Telangana, Tamil Nadu, Karnataka, and Kerala.

The rest of the seats are fairly well-distributed across the country. As of today, the states in the country that have the lower number of seats have reported high enrolment percentages, while the states with larger capacity (>25,000) have reported a lower % of enrolment in engineering, Karnataka being an exception.

1.3. Engineering Education in the state of Assam: Tiwari (2021) outlines that the first Diploma Institute was established after independence with the name of Assam Engineering Institute (AEI) at Chandmari, Guwahati and following that, the Technical Education in Jorhat started with the establishment of Prince of Wales Institute of Engineering & Technology at Jorhat before independence in 1927. At the Degree level, Assam Engineering College (AEC) was first established under the name of Assam Civil Engineering College on the same campus of AEI, Chandmari, with seventy-two students in the civil engineering branch (Tiwari, 2021). Eventually, it was relocated to its own campus in Jalukbari, Guwahati, in 1957 with the new name Assam Engineering College (AEC). Tiwari (2021) further stresses that until the creation of a separate Directorate of Technical Education (DTE) by the government of Assam on the 1st of April 1959, AEC and other technical institutions of the state were under the administrative control of the Directorate of Public Instruction (DPI). The establishment of Assam Engineering Institute and later the establishment of Assam Engineering College was the beginning of Technical Education in the State of Assam. It has been a long journey of evolution for state technical education in the State of Assam. The Directorate of Technical Education, Assam, was established in 1960. There are five Government Engineering Colleges and twenty-one Polytechnic Institutions under this Directorate. On the technical education front, there has been phenomenal growth in recent years. The first Engineering College – Assam Engineering College, was established in 1956 at Guwahati and was the first Diploma Institution. Assam Textile Institution was established in 1920 at Guwahati.

1.4. Dibrugarh University Institute of Engineering & Technology (DUIET): The Dibrugarh University Institute of Engineering & Technology (DUIET) is a constituent college of Dibrugarh University that was established in the year 2009 (DUIET Brochure,2020-21). The institute was approved by the All India Council for Technical Education and the government of Assam. The institute aims to produce the quality technocrats industrial houses require locally and internationally. Currently, DUIET offers a 4-year Bachelor of Technology Degree programme under four branches of engineering. These branches are Computer Science & Engineering, Electronics and Communication Engineering, Mechanical Engineering and Petroleum Engineering. The first three branches have an intake capacity of 60 students, and the last one has an intake capacity of 50 students. DUIET, as an integral part of Dibrugarh University, has been striving to impart quality education through an energetic team of highly experienced faculty members and technical instructors. The institute is situated within the lush green and picturesque campus of Dibrugarh University. Each department is equipped with state-of-the-art classrooms, laboratories, seminar rooms, and other teaching-learning facilities.

2. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Multiple studies reveal that there are so many inequalities in higher educational institutions, and it was found to be of utmost importance that these inequalities are well researched and known by the educational institutions and the government for the purposes of social and economic policy formulations and provision of assistance to the students. The researcher in the present study, therefore, found it to be of utmost importance to study and understand the socio-economic background of students of Dibrugarh University Institute of Engineering and Technology.

The research findings will also bring to light the institutional authorities and the university authorities at large the economic and social disparities among their students, and this will help them create an inclusive learning environment for all students regardless of their socioeconomic backgrounds. Engineering education is one of the most sought-after in India because research indicates that it has the potential to make India a leading knowledge economy in the future. This study will provide future applicants with useful information as they prepare to enroll in engineering school.

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The research was aimed at two main objectives. First, the socio-economic background and pre-enrolment preparation of B. Tech students will be studied, and second, the state regulations on the admission of students into technical institutions across Assam will be analysed.

4. METHODOLOGY

The researchers used the descriptive survey method as the study demands. The study population included all the students studying the B. Tech programme in all departments of Dibrugarh University Institute of Engineering and Technology (DUIET). The study sample included 100 B. Tech students of Dibrugarh University Institute of Engineering and Technology (DUIET) were chosen with a convenient sampling technique. The researchers also did document analysis to attain the study's second objective.

The researcher in this study used a structured, self-reporting questionnaire that was administered to students. The questionnaire comprised a total of 33 questions soliciting information on participants' socio-demographic characteristics. The questionnaire also includes questions seeking information on participants' school history such as medium of instruction, management of their school, examination board and performance indicated by percentage ranks in both class X and class XII, pre-enrolment activities, number of attempts they made before enrolling, source of their encouragement to enrol, challenges they encountered, etc. The documents such as Directorate of Technical Education (DTE) guidelines and schedule for admission in the 3rd semester B. Tech (lateral entry) programme in the engineering colleges of Assam, 2022-23, All India Council for Technical Education (AICTE) disclosure document on admissions into B. Tech programmes, including the Combined Entrance Examination (CEE) information brochure for admission into B. Tech programmes in the state of Assam and DTE-Admission rules into the 3-year Diploma engineering/technology courses in the state of Assam were analysed.

5. ANALYSIS OF DATA, RESULTS AND FINDINGS

5.1. Analysis of the state regulations on the admission of B. Tech students into colleges:

The government of Assam, through the Directorate of Technical Education, provides procedures for selecting and admitting students in the colleges. Together with the entrance exams hosting institutions, the DTE conducts the entrance examination (CEE) for candidates who want to enrol on the technical colleges of the state. While the DTE dictates rules and regulations for admission into public/government colleges, private colleges in the state also conduct their own admission process but under their own regulations and policies (Kumar, 2023). For admission of students, the DTE conducts the state-wide entrance examination popularly known as the Combined Entrance Examination (CEE). This test is mandatory for one to be considered for admission into the public colleges and universities of technical education in Assam.

The Joint Entrance Examination (JEE) is another test prepared for the students to enrol into the B. tech programme within the state. CEE scores may also be acceptable in private universities. The DTE also organises counselling for all students who are seeking admission into the B.Tech programmes. The DTE has outlined the following criteria for admission of students into the B. tech programmes

- ✓ **Domicile rule:** For a student to be eligible for admission, he/she must be a citizen of India. They must permanently reside in Assam and must have passed class 10 and 12.
- ✓ **Age limit:** The candidate must not be below 17 years of age as of August of the admission year. The upper age limit of the candidates for B. tech admission in Assam is 21 years while that of SC/ST is 25 years. For B.Sc. graduates who would like to pursue B. tech the upper age limit is 22 years.
- ✓ **Candidate qualification:** Candidates of the general category must have at least 50% marks in class 12 with mathematics, physics and chemistry as their major subjects. The candidates belonging to the reserved categories (SC/ST) should have at least 40%-45% in class 12 in the same subjects as mentioned above. The candidates should have passed all the subjects in class 12 and they should have a valid CEE rank for B. tech admission into the government colleges.
- ✓ **Exception for entrance test:** If the candidate has scored more than 85% of marks in class 12 and holds the first position. He/she is exempted from the entrance test and they are deemed eligible for direct admission into the college.

The DTE is the major stake holder in the admission process of students in the government colleges of the state for B tech degrees. It is worth mentioning that B. tech admissions in the state are bound to the reservation policies of the state. The policy is applicable to B. tech seats in the state government engineering colleges only (Kumar, 2023). The reservation policy is presented in the following table:

Table No 1: Assam B. Tech Admission Reservation Policy 2023

Name of the category	Percentage of seats reserved in Assam government engineering colleges
SC	7 %
ST (Plains)	10%
ST (Hills)	5%
OBC	As per government rules
TGLC	One seat in each college
Ex TGLC	One seat in each college
Daughter/son of Ex-serviceman	One seat in each college
PH	3%
NCC	One seat in each college
Motak/ Moran communities	One seat in each college

The government of Assam, through the DTE, also prepares a guideline and schedule for admission into 3rd semester of B. tech programmes in the government engineering colleges of the state. This entry is known as lateral entry (Directorate of Technical Education, 2022). The eligibility into a four-year B. tech program through lateral entry is as follows:

- ✓ The candidate must be an Indian citizen and a permanent resident of Assam
- ✓ They must possess a recognised Diploma of a minimum of 3 years from any polytechnic institute of Assam under the State Council of Technical Education (SCTE) or Guwahati or Assam Energy Institute, Sivsargar.
- ✓ The candidate must secure a minimum of 45% (40% in case of SC/ST) in the polytechnic course.
- ✓ They must have a valid rank in the entrance examination i.e. Joint Lateral Entrance Examination (JLEE)
- ✓ Candidate must possess good moral character.
- ✓ They must be mentally and physically fit.

5.2. Analysis of Socio-Economic status of the respondents: To study the socio-economic background of the respondents, a questionnaire was developed covering the social and economic aspects such as respondents' social demographics, their parental occupation, their parental education, Annual income, wealth and habitation.

- ❖ **Demographic character:** Out of the 100 samples, 67 were found male, and 33 were found female, which reflects the underrepresentation of females in the B.Tech course. Similarly, from the randomly taken sample, it was found that 3% of students were SC, 14% were ST, 36% were OBC, and 47% were general category. Regarding the siblings of the sample students, it is found very interesting that 52% samples were single child. 29% sample have one sibling and 19% have more than 2 siblings.
- ❖ **Parents' education and occupation:** On the educational level of the respondents, the study found that 80% of them had fathers with a higher education qualification (Diploma, bachelor's degree, Masters). It is also seen that less than 20% of the respondents' fathers had a school education. This finding reflects a very significant character of parents in both developing and underdeveloped countries who are willing to give their children the education they could not get. Regarding the education of mothers, the study found that 69% of the respondents' mothers had higher education qualifications (Diploma, bachelor's degree, masters), which is the majority. Over 30% of the respondents had mothers with secondary and primary education. These findings reveal that the majority of the respondent's parents had a graduation/higher education qualification. Over 30% of the parents only had an educational qualification of up to class XII or higher secondary. The percentage of respondents with fathers whose highest educational qualification is school education was found to be less than that of students whose mothers have school education as their highest educational qualification.
- ❖ **Parental Occupation:** Regarding the father's occupation, it was found that the majority of respondents have working fathers, with over 50% of the students having fathers who are public employees or civil servants. 46% was found to be of those respondents whose fathers work in both the private and business sectors. On the other hand, regarding the occupation of mothers, 60% of the students indicated that their mothers work in the public sector or as government employees, private sector or business sector. This indicates an important characteristic of mothers in the 21st century who believe that it is important for them to work and contribute in the family's income. However, almost half of the students were found to have mothers who are housewives. The general finding on students' parental occupation is that, amongst students sampled, those whose parents were in government occupational categories exceed 50%. Together, 68% of the respondents had fathers who are employees of both government and private sectors.

This implies that the majority of B. Tech students come from middle-class income families. Roy (2018) argues that the middle class falls in the middle of the social hierarchy and occupies a socio-economic position between the working and upper classes. Studies by international organisations such as the World Bank and Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) also maintain this definition of middle-class income families. This points to the idea that parents of the sampled students in the present study fall into this social category or social class. The total number of students whose parents are working was found to be 52%.

- ❖ **Parental Income and Wealth:** Regarding the aspect of Parental income and wealth, 67% respondents said the annual income of parents is more than 3 lakhs. 27% of the respondents had parents with an annual income between 1 lakh and 3 lakhs. This implies that the B. Tech students studying at DUIET come from middle class & lower middle-class families. The study also found that about 6% of the respondents had parental income less than 1 lakh. While the larger portion of the B. Tech students seem to be economically well-off, there is still a significant number of them with families who are not doing too well economically. Similarly, the study reveals that nearly 50% of the students' parents owned sizable plot of land and 30% of the students studied have parents who own buildings and cars. Students whose parents do not own assets is 23%. A significant number of students were found to belong to families with no assets.
- ❖ **Respondents Habitation:** Regarding their habitation, the study revealed that 90% of the respondents' family lived at their own home. And a very insignificant number of respondents' family lived in rented house. In another question of the study, it was seen that 12% of the respondent belongs to Metropolitan cities, 55% belong to towns and 33% belongs to villages. This reveals that the data concurs with multiple studies done in the developed and other developing countries that indicate that a majority of educated and working-class people tend to live in townships where there is ease access to goods and services such as health services, education, and because many of them have their places of work in townships and cities.

5.3. Analysis of the Pre-enrolments preparation of respondents to enrol into B.Tech Programme: One of the fundamental questions that this study sought to answer was the kind of preparation the students engage in order to enrol into the technical colleges of the state. The study wanted to understand educational background of students prior to enrolling into B. Tech.

- ❖ **Nature of schools attended by the respondents:** A whopping 74% of the respondents went to private schools while 26% were from public schools. While there is no comprehensive data on school fees charged by private schools in the state in current study, data from Assam State government 2022 fee structure for private and non-governmental educational organizations explicitly show that fees for private secondary education are very hefty, which means private education can be accessed by those children whose families can afford to pay for it.
- ❖ **Percentage of Marks secured in Board examination:** The findings (Table 2) show that nearly 70% of the surveyed students scored more than 70% in class X Board exams and 63% surveyed students scored more than 70% in class XII board exam. In both the exams, the respondents seemed to have done well. This could be because of the fact that majority of them come from educated families who give them support with their studies in however way possible. Research shows that students who come from educated families are far more likely to do well in their studies than those who

do not come from educated families. This finding also reflects that majority of the students enrolled in B.Tech programme are brighter and meritorious.

Table 2: Percentages of marks secured by students in class X & XII

Range of Percentage of Marks	Percentage of marks secured by the students in Class X	Percentage of marks secured by the students in Class XII
Below 60%	12	7
61% - 70%	20	30
71% - 80%	17	25
81% - 90%	34	30
91% - 100%	17	8
Total	100	100

- ❖ **Coaching as part of the Pre-enrolment preparation for B. Tech Programme:** The data obtained from the study shows that a majority of the surveyed students i.e., 55% did not take coaching. An October 2013 article by The Times of India reported that data analysed by the Joint Entrance Examination (JEE) cell reveals that while 60% of the students who made it to the seven old Indian Institute of Technology (IITs) took some form of coaching in their preparation in 2007, the following year that figure dropped from 60% to 45%. The article goes further to report that about 50% of the students prepare for the entrance examination on their own (Chhopia, 2013). It is therefore not a surprise that the majority of these students did not take any form of coaching and they were successful in their entrance examination. This however, does not discourage students from taking all the help they could get including coaching in order to crack the JEE/CEE.
- ❖ **Nature of coaching taken by respondents for enrolment into B. Tech Programme:** The above diagram presents the nature of coaching taken by the respondents. Cracking the CEE/JEE is one of the crucial conditions a candidate should satisfy for them to be considered for admission into the B. Tech programme in the state. It therefore makes sense that the study found the majority of the respondents' (55%) who opted for coaching to have taken the entrance examination coaching. Remaining 45% of the respondents took coaching in the form of career counselling only.
- ❖ **The duration of coaching taken by respondents for enrolment into B. Tech Programme:** The findings on the duration of the coaching show that coaching for the majority of those who opted for it took less than a year. It is found that coaching goes for different times for different people. This is partly because people go for coaching in different coaching centres available in the state. Only 1% students opted coaching more than a year to prepare themselves to enrol in B. Tech programme.
- ❖ **The financial expenses incurred for enrolment into B. Tech Programme:** the respondents who opted coaching were asked to present the monetary expenses incurred by them in the coaching programme. Around 84%, responded that they spent Rs 50000 rupees and less for the whole coaching programme. The remaining 12% opined that they had spent more than Rs 50 000.
- ❖ **Number of attempts in entrance exam to enrol into the B. Tech programme:** the study reveals that 78% of the respondents attempted once and were successful. The study reveals that many students do succeed to enrol at their first trial. Over half of the respondents in this present study did not opt for coaching and the majority of them succeeded to enrol into the programme at their first trial.

The finding is consistent with the reporting by The Times of India that indeed many students do succeed to enrol without taking any form of coaching. 19% respondents attempted for two times to clear the entrance for B. Tech Programme.

- ❖ **Source of encouragement to enrol into B Tech programme:** The data show that 68% of the students had their parents for encouragement and support as they navigated the preparation process into the college. Studies show that parents who are there for their children not only tend to turn out to be good human beings, but they also do exceptionally well in their academics. This study has already found that the majority of the respondents have parents with higher education degree, which means they are surrounded by people who are well informed to guide them in their studies. 11% students said school teacher as source of encouragement and 14% said friends as a source of encouragement.
- ❖ **The challenges faced by respondents as they prepared to enrol into B. Tech programme:** The study found that over 50% of the respondents faced examination challenges, 18% faced financial challenges and over 27% of them faced other challenges. It takes so much for a student to be admitted into any institution of higher learning, it takes much more for those students who have to go for coaching. There is transport expenses incurred, rent, coaching fees for some, etc. This means for families who are not well-off financially, it becomes a bit challenging for their students.

6. DISCUSSION & CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, it was revealed that majority of the surveyed B. Tech students come from middle income families looking at factors such as annual income, level of education, occupational, etc. that qualifies individuals to be classified as middle-class income families. The study revealed that over 77% of the studied students have parents who own assets and the majority of the same students have parents making an annual income of over 3 Lakhs. Assets are some of the major contributors of the family's income and this finding by the study may imply that many of these students' parents have a larger portion of their annual income coming from the assets. This may be an indication that the majority of these students come from economically well-off families. The study also found that the majority of the students have parents with graduate and post-graduate qualification. In their 2014 study, Alade et al found that parents' educational level has a great influence on the students' academic performance. The performance of the majority of the surveyed students in both class X and class XII, including their success in the entrance examination for the programme could be a result of having an educated parents helping them with their work or even motivating them to do better and be successful like their parents. Researchers in sociology and education have extensively cited parental occupation in the literature as an important proxy indicator of socio-economic status of higher education students.

Many times, people's incomes are almost always connected to their occupation hence the ability of the majority of the respondents' parents to send them to private schools, where there are fees to pay compared to public or government schools where education is almost free. These findings on parental education, income, wealth, occupation and habitation imply that the surveyed students, over 50% have a better socio-economic background and are likely to progress well in their lives. The data also reveals that many students have their parents as their biggest supporters as they make academic decision and this reflection of a good parent-child support that the many of the surveyed students have. As indicated, over 50% of the respondents said they faced examination challenges.

This is the majority of the respondents and while the data does not clearly show that this group is constituted by those respondents who did not take coaching, it is within the realm of possibility that a huge number of them are those who did not opt for coaching and deprived themselves of enough of a robust and comprehensive preparation. Nonetheless, the challenge was nothing they could not overcome as many successfully enrolled into the B. Tech programme. The findings also show that 68% of the respondents got encouragement to enrol from their parents and 32% got it from their school teachers, friends and other people. This stands to show the support that parents of the B. Tech are giving them as they navigate their academic journey. The study shows that 18% which is a small percentage of the respondents, said they faced financial challenges. This finding goes to show that the parents ensure every support for their students as they prepared for enrolling. One challenge that over 50% of the respondents indicated was examination challenges. While the data does not clearly show that this group is constituted by those respondents who did not take coaching, it is within the realm of possibility that a huge number of them are the respondents who did not go for coaching and deprived themselves of enough preparation. Nonetheless, the challenge was nothing they could not overcome as data (see fig.14) points out that nearly 80% of them successfully enrolled into the programme after one attempt. It is also worth highlighting that the study also found that 67% of the respondents did not prepare any other entrance examination besides engineering. It goes to show how much they wanted to become engineers as almost all of them stated that their main objective was to become engineers.

Individuals' socio-economic status is a very difficult issue to study for people are a bit reluctant to reveal information about themselves, yet is it also important for matters of policy where their people stand. When educational institutions like Dibrugarh University know the extent to which its student community is diverse in terms of the socioeconomic background, assistance to give who, but it also helps the institution to create a conducive learning environment that is going to be suitable for everybody. India is a massively diverse country in terms of both the social and economic positions of the citizens. However, extensive research still needs to be carried out to check the socio-economic status of people changes with the changing times and it is improving for the minority communities.

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Socio-Economic Background and Pre-Enrolment Preparation of Engineering Students: An Empirical Investigation

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